

STUDY OF FUNCTIONALIZED-GRAPHENE BASED POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES THROUGH DETAILED ATOMISTIC SIMULATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The study of graphene based nanostructured polymeric materials is an intense research area. Molecular simulations can be a valuable tool for the study of such hybrid complex materials at the molecular level. Graphene structures produced by the reduction of the graphene oxide usually contain some oxygen percentage coming mainly from the carboxyl groups remained on the edges of the graphene. With the increasing importance of the graphene in the material science, here we draw our attention to the effect of these groups on the properties of the graphene-based materials. The current work refers to a detailed multi-scale hierarchical simulation study on hybrid polymer/graphene interfacial systems. Here, we present results through detailed atomistic molecular dynamics (MD) simulations of hybrid nanostructured polymer/graphene materials for different polymer matrices. We study the behaviour of polymer nanocomposites with three types of dispersed graphene: (a) the pure non-functionalized sheet, (b) graphene with hydrogens grafted on the edges and (c) carboxyl-functionalized graphene. Data concerning the structural and dynamical properties of the polymer chains are presented. In addition, we compute the dynamic properties and the fluctuations of the particular graphene sheets and we discuss in detail the importance of the strong electrostatic interactions present in the systems. The information obtained on the molecular scale in our work contributes to the understanding of the miscibility and the mechanical properties of the graphene/polymer nanocomposites. Our work shows clearly that the structural, conformational and dynamical properties of the polymer chains diversify from their corresponding bulk behaviour, as a function of the distance from the graphene layer.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer/graphene nanocomposites have remarkable physical properties with a broad range of potential applications in many different areas. Indeed, in the last decade the graphene became one of the most studied materials. Because of its exceptional properties, it also has been considered and tested as a very promising nanofiller [1-5].

However, bad dispersion of graphene-based fillers together with problematic large-scale production of defect-free graphene remain two main obstacles in the further development of hybrid graphene-polymer materials. The most widely used method for the synthesis of graphene sheets is based on the exfoliation and further reduction of graphite oxide [3]. During the reduction process, the oxygen-containing groups grafted on the surface are chemically or thermally removed and π -conjugated system is restored. The final product is a highly conductive graphene-like structure with some eventual oxygen residues coming mainly from the carboxyl groups bonded on the edges of the sheets. These groups are supposed to be responsible for the apparent hydrophilic character of the chemically reduced graphene.

Furthermore, it is well-known that the strength of the polymer/surface interaction is the main factor in the reinforcement of the mechanical as well as rheological properties of the material [5]. In consequence, improvement in storage modulus can be tuned by a proper choice of the polymer matrix and loading of the nanofiller [5-6]. Yet, the effect of the remained oxygen groups grafted on the edges on the properties of the graphene nanocomposites remains unclear and their presence is omitted in most of the experimental works. Some simulation studies focus on the edge groups modifications and its effect on the stability and mechanical properties of the graphene sheet itself, without the presence of polymer matrix. Recently, it was shown [7] that a reduction in the Young modulus due to wrinkles in the graphene and graphene oxide sheets were observed. In case of the graphene oxide sheets, the intermolecular hydrogen bonds between edges grafted carboxyl groups induced extra buckling. Authors suggest that in polymer nanocomposites the wrinkles could be flattened by a proper stress transfer between the graphene sheet and the polymer matrix or/and by minimizing the edge effects.

Motivated by the recent advances in the graphene synthesis and graphene-based nanocomposites, we drew our attention to the polymer materials containing reduced graphene functionalized on the edges. The main idea is to preserve the π -conjugated system in graphene sheets and so its exceptional conductivity, while improving the interaction with the polymer matrix through specific functional groups.

In the current study we present results which are part of a general computational approach based on a methodology of hierarchical simulations for the study of real polymer/graphene systems. Our primary goal is the study of the effect of the graphene sheets on the structural and dynamical properties of polymers. In more details we study three hybrid polymer/graphene systems: PE/graphene, PS/graphene and PMMA/graphene using a periodic graphene sheet (infinite graphene) which remains frozen during the simulation. These are thin polymer films confined between two graphene layers. Furthermore we study systems of PE/graphene and PEO/graphene where a flexible graphene sheet of finite size is used. In the last case the graphene sheet is of three different types: a) with a partial charge distribution at the edges, b) with edge atoms functionalized with hydrogens and c) with edge atoms functionalized with carboxyl groups (reduced graphene).

We use the molecular dynamics simulations as a perfect tool for the investigation of graphene/polymer nanocomposites properties at the molecular level. By using the atomistic model, we keep the information about the chemical structure of the components and at the same time we avoid the difficulties with preparation of the graphene and its dispersion in the matrix. We present the results of fully atomistic simulations of the different hybrid graphene/polymer systems. These systems were obtained by a dispersion of two types of the reduced graphene sheet in polar or non-polar polymer matrix. The used nanofillers differ in type of the functional group attached to the edge carbon atoms of the graphene sheet, see Figure 1.

Various properties have been studied like the density profile, structural characteristics of the polymer chains as well as dynamical properties which are the focus of the current work. We study the dynamics of polymer chains both in the monomer level and the entire chain level (center of mass of the chain), recording the time evolution of the mean squared displacement, as well as through time autocorrelation functions for a vector which is defined along the polymer chain. All the examined properties are studied as a function of the distance from the graphene sheet defining in this way a series of “adsorption layers”. Moreover all the examined properties are compared to the corresponding properties of the respective bulk systems at the same conditions. Preliminary results based on the study of the wrinkling of the graphene sheet during its motion in the polymer matrix are also presented.

2 SIMULATION METHOD

The current study was based on detailed atomistic Molecular Dynamics simulations. For the case of thin polymer films, details about the force field which was used for each different polymer are given in our previous publications [8-11]. For the case of the systems with flexible graphene sheets of finite size, an all atom model was used. In this model partial charges are placed on all the terminal atoms of the graphene sheet (type a) [11]. For graphene flakes with hydrogen or carboxyl groups at the end atoms (types b and c), the corresponding force fields are described in reference [11]. The concentration

of graphene in the polymer matrix is 3% wt. Simulations are carried out at constant pressure of $P=1\text{atm}$ and temperature $T=450\text{K}$ for PE, $T=500\text{K}$ for PS and PMMA and $T=318\text{K}$ for PEO.

Figure 1: Visualization of the simulated molecules: a) hydrogenated sheet b) carboxylated sheet c) polyethylene and d) polyethylene oxide. Carbon groups are illustrated by cyan, oxygens by red and hydrogens by grey colour.

Figure 2: Division of the space around the graphene sheet in the analysis: parallel regions (illustrated by the full lines) and edges.

A different analysis scheme has been used for the case of the periodic graphene sheet (“infinite graphene”) and the systems with the finite graphene layers. In the first case the various properties have been studied as a function of the distance from the graphene flake using the definition of layers parallel to the sheet of specific thickness (binning), which can have a different value depending on the property under investigation. In the second case the analysis has been performed in radial distances measured from the center of mass of the graphene. In this way spherical shells of increasing radius are created. Again the thickness of the spherical shell diversifies according to the studied property.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following we present results of dynamics for the systems that we study, dividing into two general categories: a) Confined polymer films where we use periodic graphene sheets (“infinite size”), which remain frozen during the simulations [8-10] and b) Finite size graphene sheets which move freely in the polymer matrix [11,12].

3.1 Polymer Films Confined between Graphene Sheets

Three systems of thin polymer films of the same thickness were studied: PE/graphene, PS/graphene and PMMA/graphene [2,4]. A comparison among the three different polymers is based on a vector which is defined along the backbone of the polymer chain and connects two non-consecutive carbon atoms (v_{BB}). We observe a time autocorrelation function of this vector expressed by the second Legendre polynomial:

$$P_2(t) = 3(\langle \cos^2 \theta(t) \rangle - 1) / 2$$

as a function of the distance from the graphene sheet (adsorption layers). Then we fit each curve with a Kohlrausch-Williams-Watts (KWW) function:

$$P_2(t) = A \exp(-(t/t_{KWW})^\beta)$$

from which the segmental relaxation time is extracted through the relation: $\tau_{seg} = (t_{KWW}/\beta)\Gamma(1/\beta)$, where $\Gamma()$ is the gamma function.

Furthermore the values of the β -exponent provide important information for the distribution of the relaxation times, or in other words the deviation of the behavior of the system from the ideal Debye behavior which stands for $\beta=1$. Segmental relaxation times (τ_{seg}) as a function of the distance from the graphene layer, for the three different polymers, are depicted in Figure 3a. A qualitative similar behavior is observed for all three systems though, clear quantitative differences are detected. The monomers which are very close to the graphene sheet are much slower compared to the more distant monomers. Therefore graphene sheet induced a retardation of dynamics which results in very large values of the relaxation times at short distances. In the following relaxation times are reduced gradually and attain the values of the corresponding bulk systems at long distances from graphene (dashed horizontal lines in Figure 1a). Quantitative comparisons among the three polymers reveal PE the fastest of the three systems, which reaches the corresponding bulk value after almost 2nm from the surface, PS follows at almost 3nm, while PMMA is the slowest one, it attains its bulk value at about 4nm from the graphene sheet. The values for the corresponding β -exponents, which are depicted in Figure 3b, do not present any specific quantitative difference among the three systems. However, the values are lower close to the interface and higher at longer distances, where the corresponding bulk values are almost attained within statistical uncertainties (± 0.05). This behavior is indicative of a broader distribution of relaxation times close to the graphene layer.

Figure 3: (a) Segmental relaxation time for the characteristic vector v_{BB} , based on the time autocorrelation function $P_2(t)$ for PS, PMMA and PE polymer/graphene hybrid systems, as a function of the distance from the graphene sheet. (b) The exponent β , as it is extracted from the fit with KWW functions for all three systems.

3.2 Graphene based Polymer Nanocomposites: Graphene sheets dispersed in Polymer matrix

In the following we study the dynamics for a polymer/graphene system, where one graphene sheet of type (a) and of finite size (49×51) \AA^2 , is moving in a PE matrix. Calculation of the segmental relaxation time for the same vector (v_{BB}) as in the previous subsection leads to Figure 4a,b. Values of

the corresponding bulk system are also included in Figure 4 with dashed lines. It is also obvious in this case that polymer chains close to graphene (up to almost 0.5nm) have slower dynamics compared to the rest of the film. At these distances τ_{seg} is almost 10 times larger than the bulk value. At longer distances monomers move more freely leading to an almost constant value of τ_{seg} beyond 4.0-5.0nm. This is a similar qualitative behavior to that of the confined thin PE film, though the quantitative comparison of the two curves, shown in Figure 4a reveals a faster dynamics at short distances for the system with the finite graphene sheet (nanocomposite). Moreover the values for the exponent β are smaller compared to the bulk polymer at any distance from graphene (Figure 4b). This shows a broader distribution of the segmental relaxation times even at long distances from the graphene layer where the values for the times have reached the corresponding bulk value. This aspect of dynamical heterogeneities existing in the nanocomposite polymer systems seem to be even more complex than that in the case of the confined between two graphene layers polymer chains for which the behavior at long distances from the surface is similar to bulk.

Figure 4: (a) Segmental relaxation time for the characteristic vector v_{BB} , based on the time autocorrelation function $P_2(t)$ for PE as a function of the radial distance from the center of mass of the graphene sheet. (b) The exponent β , as it is extracted from the fit with KWW functions. Dashed horizontal lines correspond to the bulk PE values for τ_{seg} and β at the same conditions.

Next, we study in more detail the *spatial and dynamical heterogeneities* of the polymer/graphene hybrid systems. In order to demonstrate the heterogeneities in the dynamics in the system, we divided the simulation box into cubical regions and assigned segments to particular cells. Then we calculated the absolute displacement $d_i = |r_i(t + t_0) - r_i(t_0)|$ of the segments at time $t = 1$ ns in every region and obtained the main value d by averaging over all segmental displacements in the cell. After, we applied a colour scheme for the cells according to their d values as it is explained on the right side of Figure 5. In this representation, different mobility of segments placed in particular parts of nanocomposite is visible. Namely, we can see in both nanocomposites low values of the displacement in the vicinity of the graphene sheets.

Interestingly, while in the case of the hydrogenated sheet the slow segments are mainly placed below and above the graphene filler, in case of the carboxylated sheet the slowest segmental dynamics can be found close to the edges of the sheet. This behaviour was observed in different snapshots (different origins t_0) and particularly for the PEO matrix. It implies that specific interactions between carboxylated groups and polar matrix may affect the local dynamics in the nanocomposites.

For the case of graphene sheets functionalized with hydrogen atoms (b) the slower monomers (those with the shortest displacement from the closest to them atom of graphene) are observed to be

above and below the graphene layer in parallel to the graphene planes. Moreover there is a gradual increase of their dynamics with the increasing distance from the graphene. This behavior is qualitative similar with the one of the confined polymer films as well as the nanocomposites with graphene flakes of type (a). On the contrary for the systems with graphene flakes of type (c) the slowest monomers are observed around the edges of the graphene due to their electrostatic interactions with the carboxyl groups.

Figure 5: Configurations of systems of Poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO)/graphene (a) functionalized graphene with carboxyl groups. (b) functionalized graphene with hydrogen atoms. d : is the displacement of the PEO monomers from the closest to them atom of graphene. Snapshots showing absolute segmental displacement for the PEO matrix after 1ns averaged over segments placed in the same cubic cell. The simulation box was divided into $7 \times 7 \times 7$ cubic subcells.

In the next stage we calculated the end-to-end correlation functions for the chains of both matrices. The results are plotted in Figure 6 with different colours corresponding to different layers, in accordance with the colour code in Fig. 2. A simple comparison of the time scales characteristic for every polymer matrix (see x-axes in Figure 6) reveal that in general the relaxation of the PE chains is about an order of magnitude faster than the relaxation of PEO chains. In both cases of polar and non-polar matrix there is a significant slowing down of the dynamics as we approach the graphene surface (compare cyan and red lines). While the chains in the last layer relax in the same way as chains in bulk (data not shown), the decorrelation of the end-to-end vectors in the layers close to graphene sheet is shifted to longer times. In the region parallel to the graphene the change in the dynamic behaviour is caused by the adsorption of the chains on the surface. In the system of the carboxylated graphene dispersed in PEO, the specific interaction between the edge groups and matrix is responsible for even slower relaxation of the chains in the edge region than in the adsorbed layer. For the rest of the nanocomposites this phenomenon is not observed and in general the difference between the relaxation of the chains in the first and last layer of the edge region is not so pronounced. Apart from the specific interactions the mechanical interlocking between the functional groups attached to the graphene and polymer matrix may be another factor present in our systems, especially in case of the non-polar PE matrix and bulky COOH groups. It was shown that this factor plays a role in the enhancement of the mechanical properties of nanocomposites [6].

Figure 6: Comparison of the end-to-end correlation functions of the chains belonging to the layers in parallel region (solid lines) and edges (dashed lines). The upper plot shows the comparison for the PEO matrix and in the bottom the data for the PE matrix are presented.

In addition to the local properties, we also examined the overall properties of our hybrid materials. Data are shown in Figure 7. In particular, we turned our attention to the rheological properties that are very important for the industrial production of the graphene-based nanocomposites. However, well-defined and well-dispersed experimental graphene/polymer systems are rare and simulation studies face the problem of the limited computer time and memory. One well-known property measured by linear rheology is the stress relaxation modulus $G(\omega)$ as a function of frequency ω . Stress relaxation modulus in time domain $G(t)$ can be obtained from the simulation by using Green-Kubo formula.

The main problem related to the calculation of the stress autocorrelation is its noisy character. It can be improved by averaging over various simulations, in our case 10 for PEO systems and 15 for PE systems. The results for the PEO nanocomposites are shown on the left side of Figure 7. The data are plotted together with the curve for the bulk polyethylene oxide (blue colour). After the fluctuations caused by bond vibrations at short time scales, the curves for all the systems overlap. PEO chains are very short, well below the entanglement length, therefore no plateau in $G(t)$ is expected. The comparison of the data in terminal region ($t \sim 10^3$ ps) is tricky, because of a huge statistical error. However, polymer terminal relaxation times can be estimated also from the end-to-end correlation function (see above the formula) averaged over all polymer chains in the system. This function is presented on the right side of Figure 7. It is evident that the curves for the nanocomposites follow the

curve for the bulk polymer and only small deviations within the error bars are observed. In other words, the relaxation of the polymer matrix is not influenced by the presence of the graphene sheet.

Figure 7: Left: Stress relaxation modulus, calculated with the time correlator [19]. Right: Overall end-to-end correlation function averaged over whole polymer matrix.

We expect that similar behaviour would be detected in the terminal region of the $G(t)$ function. The same conclusions can be made for PE systems. One reason for no significant reinforcement of the rheological properties in our hybrid systems may be the weak interaction between the polymer and the surface. We have seen an evidence of PE and PEO adsorption on the graphene, but the adsorption is weakened by thermal fluctuations and wrinkling of the sheet. In a very recent paper Liao and co-workers claim that very strong interaction as a covalent bonding to the graphene surface is needed in order to affect the glass transition temperature of the graphene/polymer nanocomposites [13]. Experimental observations are in good agreement with the results reported in this work.

Another explanation of our results on rheology could be associated to a relatively small loading of the graphene in our systems. Nanocomposites with higher loadings and improved $\pi - \pi$ interactions between the graphene and the matrix have been prepared and analyzed and will be an object of our future study. We performed detailed atomistic simulations of reduced graphene sheets dispersed in polar and non-polar polymer matrices. Particular attention was paid on the specific interactions between functional groups grafted on the edges of graphene and the polymer matrix and their effect on nanocomposite properties. We observed differences in local dynamics between the hydrogenated and carboxylated sheets, but their impact on the overall properties was negligible. No significant reinforcement of the rheological properties was found for the graphene/polymer hybrid systems with the loadings in the range 1.7-3.6 wt%.

3.3 Wrinkling of Graphene

Finally, some preliminary results, concerning conformational characteristics of the graphene sheets in terms of fluctuations – wrinkling behavior, are presented. For this purpose we define one cross line on the sheet, parallel to the y -direction (Figure 8) and observe its motion during the simulation starting from a completely straight line (i.e., a planar conformation of the graphene sheet).

A “wavy” motion is observed with crests and troughs, as it is observed in the characteristic snapshot of Figure 8. This is a combinatory result of thermal fluctuations as well as fluctuations imposed by the (attractive) energetic interactions between the graphene and the polymer matrix. The motion of this line at different times is presented for the system with a graphene sheet of $(49 \times 51) \text{ \AA}^2$ area in Figure 8, where we have chosen four time points together with the initial snapshot ($t=0$). This is only a qualitative picture in which various shapes of the line are observed. It is interesting to see that there are cases where only crests or only troughs are detected and cases where crests and troughs exist in the same line. More detailed analysis of the wrinkling of graphene sheets in polymer/graphene nanocomposites is in progress.

Figure 8: (Left) The out of plane motion of the cross line defined on the graphene sheet for all the atoms of the line at four different time spots (colored symbols), together with the initial snapshot (black symbols, $t=0$) for the system with is $(49 \times 51) \text{ \AA}^2$ graphene sheet. (Right) A schematic representation for the conformational analysis of graphene sheets, and a characteristic snapshot of a graphene layer with fluctuations.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the current study we present results concerning the way that graphene affects the dynamical properties of various hybrid polymer/graphene systems using detailed atomistic Molecular Dynamics simulations. The systems under investigation were: a) confined thin polymer films (PE, PS, PMMA) with periodic graphene sheets which were frozen during the simulation and b) Graphene flakes of finite size moving freely in a polymer matrix (PE, PEO). In the second case the graphene sheet is of three different types: a) with a partial charge distribution at the edges, b) functionalized with hydrogens and c) functionalized with carboxyl groups.

In all cases a heterogeneous dynamics of the polymer is observed due to the presence of the graphene flake. At close to the graphene distances a retardation of the dynamics of the polymer chains is observed whereas at longer distances polymer dynamics approaches the one of the corresponding bulk system. Quantitative differences among the different polymers are found.

In the second case the effect of the terminal groups at the edges of the graphene flake is revealed. Among the three types of functionalized graphene that we study only in the case of the reduced graphene (c) (carboxyl groups at the edges) a qualitative differentiation in polymer dynamics is observed, in terms of the distribution of the monomers according to their distance from graphene. More specifically, for the case of a hybrid PEO/graphene system with graphene sheets of type (c), the slowest monomers (the ones with the shortest displacement from the closest to them graphene atom) are those which are close to the edges of graphene due to the electrostatic interactions of polymer with the carboxyl groups. On the contrary for the rest of the systems the slowest monomers are above and below the graphene sheet in parallel planes.

Current work concerns the extension of the above studies over larger polymer/graphene systems through the application of hierarchical multi-scale approaches [14-15].

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. S. Novoselov, A. K. Geim, S. V. Morozov, D. Jing, Y. Zhang, S. V. Dubonos, I. V. Grigorieva and [2] A. A. Firsov, *Science*, **306**, 2004, pp. 666.
- [2] J. Du and H.-M. Cheng. The fabrication, properties, and uses of graphene/polymer composites. *Macromolecular Chemistry and Physics*, **213**(10-11), 2012, pp. 1060–1077.
- [3] R. S. Edwards and K. S. Coleman. Graphene synthesis: relationship to applications, *Nanoscale*, **5**, 2013, pp. 38–51.
- [4] M. El Achaby, F.-E. Arrakhiz, S. Vaudreuil, A. el Kacem Qaiss, M. Bousmina, and O. Fassi-Fehri. Mechanical, thermal, and rheological properties of graphene-based polypropylene nanocomposites prepared by melt mixing. *Polymer Composites*, **33**, 2012, pp.733–744.
- [5] K. Hu, D. D. Kulkarni, I. Choi, and V. V. Tsukruk. Graphene-polymer nanocomposites for structural and functional applications, *Progress in Polymer Science*, **39**, 2014, pp. 1934 – 1972. Topical Issue on Nanocomposites.
- [6] C. Lv, Q. Xue, D. Xia, M. Ma, J. Xie, and H. Chen. Effect of chemisorption on the interfacial bonding characteristics of graphene-polymer composites, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*, **114**, 2010, pp. 6588–6594.
- [7] X. Shen, X. Lin, N. Yousefi, J. Jia, and J.-K. Kim. Wrinkling in graphene sheets and graphene oxide papers, *Carbon*, **66**, 2014, pp. 84 – 92.
- [8] A.N. Rissanou, and V. Harmandaris, Structure and dynamics of poly(methyl methacrylate)/graphene systems through atomistic molecular dynamics simulations, *J Nanopart Res.*, **15**, 2013, pp. 1589:1-14.
- [9] A.N. Rissanou, and V. Harmandaris, A Molecular Dynamics Study of Polymer/Graphene Nanocomposites, *Macromol. Symp.*, **331-332**, 2013, pp. 43-49.
- [10] A.N. Rissanou, and V. Harmandaris, Dynamics of various polymer–graphene interfacial systems through atomistic molecular dynamics simulations, *Soft Matter.*, **10**, 2014, pp. 2876–2888.
- [11] A.N. Rissanou, A.J. Power, and V. Harmandaris, Properties of Polyethylene/Graphene Nanocomposites through Molecular Dynamics Simulations, *Polymers*, **7**, 2015, pp. 390-417.
- [12] P. Bacova, A.N. Rissanou, and V. Harmandaris, Properties of functionalized graphene based polymer nanocomposites through detailed atomistic simulations, to be submitted.
- [13] K.-H. Liao, S. Aoyama, A. A. Abdala, and C. Macosko, Does graphene change tg of nanocomposites? *Macromolecules*, **47**, 2014, pp. 8311–8319.
- [14] V. Harmandaris, K. Kremer, Predicting polymer dynamics at multiple length and time scales, *Soft Matter* **5**, 2009, 3920-3926.
- [15] V. Harmandaris, K. Kremer, Dynamics of polystyrene melts through hierarchical multiscale simulations, *Macromolecules*, **42**, 2010, pp. 791-802.